

Synthetic biology discourse on Twitter

Brandon Sepulvado¹ and Lilian Huang²

¹ sepulvado-brandon@norc.org

4350 East-West Highway, 8th Floor, Bethesda, Maryland, 20814 (USA)

² huang-lilian@norc.org

55 East Monroe Street, 30th Floor, Chicago, Illinois, 60603 (USA)

Abstract

Synthetic biology is a multifaceted field that spans disciplines, sectors, and industries, but, despite this fact, much bibliometric knowledge about synthetic biology comes from a focus on scholarly literature. This paper investigates discourse about synthetic biology on Twitter because it is a popular platform for synthetic biology stakeholders and because it captures a diverse range of topics surrounding synthetic biology. Using hierarchical stochastic blockmodels and community detection, we investigate the range of synthetic biology topics discussed on Twitter and the general structure of the discourse. Major findings include that discussion of synthetic biology on Twitter largely focuses on non-scholarly topics, that there is a wide range of topics discussed, and that the hashtags used to organize synthetic biology Twitter discourse form a sparse network of many disconnected clusters. We conclude with a discussion of the implications of these findings for the bibliometric literature on synthetic biology and note future work to be undertaken as a result of this inquiry.

Introduction

Synthetic biology involves the editing and redesign of organisms and their components, and the field brings together different sectors and academic disciplines (Bauer & Bogner, 2020; Endy, 2005; Keiper & Atanassova, 2020). For example, many synthetic biologists work to address public health and medical challenges, which necessitates participation from pharmaceutical companies. New startups regularly emerge, seeking to commercialize innovations that originate from academic labs, and the labs are often dependent upon private companies for raw materials and to store the output of experiments. This organization of professional activities by different types of actors has been called a field (Bourdieu, 1973) or linked ecologies (Abbott, 2016).

Given this diversity of actors involved and the myriad societal challenges they seek to address, it is perhaps surprising that previous scientometric studies tend to focus on scholarly literature (Hu & Rousseau, 2015; Raimbault et al., 2016; Shapira et al., 2017). Raimbault et al. (2016) show for example that synthetic biology—as captured through scientific literature and the authors involved in its production—began to stabilize around 2010. This information is necessary to understand the production of certain forms of synthetic biology knowledge and part of the synthetic biology workforce, yet social media studies of science (Costas, 2017) suggests that such an approach neglects non-academic actors and other data relevant to scientific/research communication.

Inspired by social media studies of science, we seek in this paper to understand synthetic biology discourse on social media; notably, this observational study examines whether traditional approaches to almetrics—focusing narrowly on research output and topics—can adequately capture communication surrounding synthetic biology. We use a keyword-based query strategy to obtain a corpus of posts from Twitter. We then analyze this corpus using network analysis, specifically hierarchical stochastic blockmodels to understand the topics discussed and community detection to understand how hashtags organize synthetic biology discourse on Twitter. The following section provides a description of the data and how they were collected.

Data

Data used in the analyses below were collected from Twitter. Not only is Twitter a common social media platform for scientific communication (Haustein, 2019; Haustein et al., 2014), but it is also a platform heavily used by actors from the synthetic biology community, including academics, industry researchers, companies, and regulators. We focus on tweets from 1 January 2010 through 30 September 2022, choosing to begin with 2010 because previous studies (Raimbault et al., 2016) have shown that synthetic biology began to stabilize around this period.

Similarly to how keywords have been used to query scholarly literature (i.e., bibliometric) databases to obtain publications relevant to synthetic biology (Hu & Rousseau, 2015; Shapira et al., 2017), we used keywords and hashtags collect relevant tweets. Hashtags are useful for collecting posts about synthetic biology because they allow users to participate in and find information about ongoing discussions on the platform without having to interact directly with other users engaged in the discourse. Hashtag enable “discussions” that combine informal commentary, presentations of fact or findings, and concerted arguments (e.g., by government agencies). For this reason, hashtags have been described as “user-generated collaborative argument[s]” (Papacharissi & de Fatima Oliveira, 2012, p. 3).

The following query was used: #synbio OR #syntheticbiology OR "synthetic biology" OR synbio OR (iGEM -igemcity) OR (#iGEM -(#igemcity)).¹ Synbio is commonly used as shorthand to refer to synthetic biology. iGEM stands for the International Genetically Engineered Machines competition. High school students, undergraduates, postgraduate students, and individuals from community labs undertake projects that they present during the yearly competition, and the projects are judged according to criteria related to technical standards as well as the students’ outreach and efforts to understand the societal implications of their research.

Figure 1. Monthly tweet counts by keyword or hashtag.

Figure 1 illustrates monthly tweet counts during the period of interest. There is an overall increase in the number of tweets each month, though the trends differ for the phrases and hashtags included in the query. Despite irregular ebbs and flows, use of the phrase “synthetic biology” increased between 2010 and 2015, but its increase in use slowed after that point; #syntheticbiology gained some popularity starting in 2018 but remains unpopular in absolute

¹ “-igemcity” was used to exclude tweets from a community of users unrelated to synthetic biology.

terms. Synbio and #synbio exhibit a different trend. Unlike with synthetic biology and its associated hashtag, synbio and #synbio did not begin to gain popularity until 2013, but they matched the popularity of “synthetic biology” by 2015-2016, even surpassing it in popularity in certain years. Mentions of “synbio” and #synbio were quite similar until 2020, after which #synbio dropped slightly in use. #iGEM has remained relatively unpopular throughout the study period. “iGEM” increased in popularity since 2010 but exhibits periodicity, in line with competition dates throughout the year. The largest number of tweets occurs late each year, which is when the iGEM competition occurs, and the tweet count typically drops to its lowest point early each year. Tweets around the 2018 and 2021 competitions were particularly popular, with the peaks for other competitions since 2015 being similar.

Methods

We take two methodological approaches to understanding synthetic biology discourse on Twitter. The first approach analyzes tweets’ text, using hierarchical stochastic blockmodels (hSBMs) to identify topic discussed. The motivation for using hSBMs to identify topics discussed is to focus on what is said rather than the structure of Twitter discourse about synthetic biology. The second approach uses network analysis to understand which hashtags are used together. Because hashtags function as common labels used by individuals and organizations to connect their posts to broader conversations and to search existing posts on the platform, the motivation to examine hashtag networks is primarily to understand the structure of Twitter synthetic biology discourse.

Topic identification

We used hSBMs to identify the topics discussed within our tweet corpus. hSBMs are an unsupervised method in which users obtain information on the topics discussed within the corpus, without having to specify before the number or content of topics. Unlike topic models, such as Latent Dirichlet Allocation, hSBMs rely upon a principled specification of their Bayesian priors, better model known statistical properties of texts, do not require the user to specify the number of topics in the corpus, and identify hierarchical relationships among topics (Gerlach et al., 2018). Topics are identified as clusters of words that co-occur in texts more frequently with each other than they do with words outside the cluster. We preprocessed tweets by removing emojis, URLs, numbers, hashtags, account mentions, retweets, and non-English tweets and by making all text lowercase. After preprocessing, there were 396,154 tweets.

Hashtag network

We created a network from hashtags. Initially, the network was constructed as an undirected bipartite graph in which hashtags were connected to the tweets in which the hashtags were used; we then projected it to a one mode network in which hashtags were connected to each other if they were used in the same tweets. Edges in the one mode hashtag network were weighted by the number of tweets in which the two adjacent nodes (i.e., hashtags) were used together. We use the Louvain algorithm (Blondel et al., 2008) to identify communities within the hashtag network; communities in this context correspond to sets of hashtags that are used more frequently with each other than with other hashtags.

Results

Topic identification

The hSBM identifies four levels to the topic hierarchy. The levels of the hierarchy might be conceived as differing levels of abstractness or granularity; moving down the hierarchy, each higher-level topic is broken down into topics at the lower level. The top level (i.e., level 4) has 25 topics, and the level below (i.e., level 3) has 84 topics. Level 2 of the topic hierarchy contains

230, and level 1—the most granular level—has 924 topics. Level 4 topics touch on issues, such as the iGEM competition, biotechnology and entrepreneurship, global markets, genomics research, stories in the news, molecular engineering research, and popular science. Topics at level four are very general. Topic level 1 contains very specific topics, sometimes even splitting topics that might make sense as a single rather than multiple topics. Examples include discussion about sustainability, specifically relating to biofuels, and the market performance of biotech companies, including both startups and established corporations. The latter actually constitutes multiple topics at level 1; it is possible to see generic terms related to market performance alongside references to specific company names or abbreviations. Other topics discuss research with specific organizations, such as pseudomonas. Table 1 provides three example topics and five keywords associated with each topic for the four levels. The major finding is the relative (un)popularity of non-academic topics relative to topics about economics and the societal impacts of synthetic biology.

Table 1. Example topic names and keywords associated with each topic for each topic level.

<i>Level</i>	<i>Topic</i>	<i>Keywords</i>
1	Sustainability	Sustainability, climate change, sustainable, biofuels, environment
1	Bioprinting	Printing, bioprinting laser, ink
1	Gender and Leadership	Leaders, inspiring, women, women in STEM, celebrate
2	Startups	Company, series b, round, seed, venture
2	Treatment	Covid, cancer, cell therapy, coronavirus, immunotherapy
2	Impact of Food Tech	Regulation, GMOs, species, biodiversity, extinct
3	Bioeconomy	Biotech, biotechnology, bioeconomy, bioengineering, synbiobeta
3	iGEM	iGEM, teams, students, competition, jamboree
3	ELSI	Public, policy, social, issues, ethics
4	iGEM	iGEM, teams, students, competition, international
4	International Markets	Symbiose, market, global, industry, development, companies
4	Genetic Engineering	Engineering, genetic, technology, protein, molecular

Hashtag network

The hashtag network is composed of 53,944 hashtags. It is not very dense, having a density of 0.00023. Of these almost 54,000 hashtags, 6,141 were not used alongside other hashtags (i.e., were isolates). Table 2 presents the 20 hashtags with the highest degree, which corresponds to those that are most frequently used alongside other hashtags. The top four represent part of the query; iGEM is also present in the table. Although this fact means that they would be expected to likely be the most frequently used hashtags in the corpus, it does not mean that we would expect them to be the highest degree hashtags because it makes no assumption about the relationship of these hashtags with other hashtags. The most frequently used hashtags largely overlap with those in Table 2. The remaining hashtags in Table 2 mention biotechnology, general topics, such as biology and science, and technologies, such as AI and CRISPR. The Louvain community detection algorithm identified 1,250 communities, excluding isolates. The largest community has 10,691 hashtags within it, representing 19.8% of all hashtags.

Table 2. Top 20 hashtags and the number of other hashtags with which they were used.

<i>Hashtag</i>	<i>Number with which Used</i>	<i>Hashtag</i>	<i>Number with which Used</i>
synbio	16829	DNA	2455
syntheticbiology	10112	Synbio	2341
SyntheticBiology	6853	biotechnology	2248
SynBio	6619	CRISPR	2247
biotech	4807	synthetic	2239
iGEM	4585	AI	2135
biology	4394	research	1700
igem	3946	innovation	1675
science	3228	Synthetic	1592
Biology	2492	Biotechnology	1567

Discussion

The goal of the analyses presented in this paper was to gain an understanding of communication surrounding synthetic biology on Twitter, particularly whether an approach focusing largely on research products and topics (i.e., that assumed by traditional altmetrics) adequately represents synthetic biology communication. Although prior bibliometric studies of synthetic biology provided useful insight into the field's scholarly emergence and evolution, social media studies of science emphasize a holistic approach to communication around science, including looking at broader data sources and expanding focus to more than only scholarly products. One initial finding from Figure 1 is that growth of tweets about synthetic biology seems to really take off around 2013 for certain hashtags and phrases, and for multiple hashtags and phrases the rate of growth slows around 2015-2016. These trends are notably different from what has been described for scholarly synthetic biology literature (Raimbault et al., 2016) and warrants further scrutiny in future analyses.

This study's analyses reveal interesting findings in terms of the topics discussed in tweets and the organization of synthetic biology Twitter discussion via hashtags. There are two major takeaways from the hSBM analyses. First, there are many topics, even at the most "abstract" level of topics. The 25 topics at this level suggest a somewhat fragmented discourse, and this notion is reinforced by how quickly the number of topics increases when descending the topic hierarchy to the more concrete or granular levels. Second, synthetic biology discourse on Twitter is largely characterized by "non-scholarly" topics. Such themes range from the social, environmental, and ethical implications of synthetic biology research to legal regulation and economic benefits of commercializing synthetic biology innovations.

The hashtag network analysis revealed a decentralized structure to synthetic biology discourse on Twitter. The hashtags form over 1,200 groupings, the largest of which was only less than one fifth of the network, and the network density is very low. The most frequently used hashtags and those that are used most frequently with other hashtags signify relatively broad conversations, referring for example to synthetic biology generally, iGEM, biology, science, biotechnology, and innovation. Hashtags that mention more concrete topics and those bringing up non-academic topics tend to be used in conjunction with the more general and popular hashtags.

The results of the topic identification and hashtag network analysis suggest that additional research is needed. Understanding communication around synthetic biology on social media requires a non-traditional bibliometric approach because of the diversity of actors and topics involved. Even an approach to altmetrics that focuses on research objects (e.g., with DOIs) is insufficient because research objects are not a popular item of discussion. Similarly, because discussion is so decentralized, gaining a thorough understanding of discourse around specific topics will require extensive work with stakeholders, so that researchers can understand the how their communities frame their discussions. Relatedly, work should build on the current study to identify motivations of social media use among synthetic biologists, as the topics identified here do not necessarily isolate what actors seek to gain from social media use (e.g., publicity, new connections, etc.), though some are suggestive (e.g., publicity for the iGEM competition). Future work will also investigate queries incorporating additional hashtags and keywords.

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